

RESEARCH STUDY

Recommendations

on local public e-services to be developed

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Authors:

RN Dr. Vratislav Datel - Expert, Czech Republic

Dr. Krzysztof Atlasiewicz - Expert, Poland

Ing. Vladimir Benko - Expert, Slovakia

Dr. hab. Anatol Gremalschi - Institutul de Politici Publice, Chişinău

Ion Coşuleanu - [Information Society Development Institute](#), Chişinău

Anastasia Ştefaniţa - [Information Society Development Institute](#), Chişinău

Dr. Igor Cojocar - [Information Society Development Institute](#), Chişinău

Editorial team:

Irina Cojocar - [Information Society Development Institute](#), Chişinău

Dr. Elena Ungureanu - [Information Society Development Institute](#), Chişinău

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© **Information Society Development Institute**

Academiei 5A str., Chisinau MD - 2028, Republic of Moldova

Tel: +373 22 289 839

Fax: +373 22 289 849

E-mail: idsi@asm.md

www.idsi.md

Table of contents

Abbreviations.....	4
1. Introduction	5
2. General notions concerning public services	7
3. Legal framework of (local) public services in Moldova	8
4. E-services.....	10
5. E-Services in Moldova - the actual situation.....	15
6. Recommendations - useful/ practical tips.....	19
6.1 Comments and Recommendations of the Polish expert	22
6.2 Comments and Recommendations of the Czech expert	24
6.3 Comments and Recommendations from Slovak expert	28
6.4 Comments and Recommendations from the national expert.....	30
Final conclusions	32
Final Recommendations	32
Bibliography	33
Annex 1. Workshop Agenda	34
Annex 2. Project Factsheet no.5	36

Abbreviations

DISCUS - Discussion on Information Society Building Issues Platform

ISDI/IDSI - Information Society Development Institute, Moldova

V4 - Visegrad countries

ICT - Information & Communication Technologies

ISPA - Information System of the Public Administration

CMS – Content Management System

LPA – Local Public Authorities

IDNO – Juridical Person Identification Number

IDNP – Physical Person Identification Number

RM – Republic of Moldova

UNDP – United Nations Development Program

ITIL – Information Technology Infrastructure Library

ISO – International Standardization Organisation

TOGAF – The Open Group Architecture Framework

WGAG – Web Content Accessibility Guidelines

IEC – International Electrotechnical Commission

ESC – European Standardisation Committee

ETSI – European Telecommunications Standards Institute

1. Introduction

The Report for the third DISCUS event – workshop: Electronic Local Public Services held on September 22-23, 2015 in Chisinau, Moldova shall be based on:

- Approved DISCUS Project Document,
- TOR provisions,
- Own experience on best practices in Visegrad countries in ICT solutions for local services (with focus on planning and strategic aspects),
- Analysed V4/EU countries experience/initiatives relevant to the DISCUS project objectives,
- Analysis of presented information and discussions during the workshop,
- Analysis of issues, solutions, plans proposed by the local authorities representatives and other stakeholders expressed during the workshop,
- Analysis of ideas expressed during informal communication at the workshop.

The research study “**Recommendations on local e-services to be developed**” is written within the DISCUS project as the result of the workshop: **Electronic Local Public Services**.

The main goal of this research study is to present the results of the workshop from September on Electronic Local Public Services. Firstly is made a short analysis of the event. The chapter 2 presents general notions about public services. After general definitions of public services, an analysis of the legal framework for public services in Moldova is presented, with an accent on local services. The chapter 4: e-services presents the concept of services based on ICT, the principles, criteria for selection, how to plan a n e-service at local level. The next paragraph is about actual situation of e-services in Moldova, followed by some practical tips. Visegrad experts formulated several comments and recommendations based on first 3 DISCUS events.

The workshop took place on September 22-23, in Chisinau. The event was attended by 50 participants, including representatives of 36 town/villages halls from Moldova - mayors, deputy mayors, specialists in various areas. Also at the event have participated representatives of academic sector, central government, civil society, national experts and international experts from Visegrad countries.

The workshop had a practical character, the working teams were coordinated by 4 experts: 3 from Visegrad countries – Poland, Slovakia and Czech Republic; and the national expert from Moldova. The discussions focused on the Action plan for implementation of local electronic services. The workshop lasted one and a half days, participants having the possibility for networking, brainstorming of ideas and exchange of experience.

The **main goal** of the event was to develop action plans by the moldovan local public servants under the guidance of Visegrad experts.

The **objective of the workshop** was to inform and raise awareness among moldovan local public servants on the need to develop and implement action plans for local electronic services, as well as to train practical skills of participants in planning and discussing an action plan concept.

The welcome speeches were delivered by dr. Igor Cojocaru – director of Information Society Development Institute, Andrei Cușcă – deputy head of the Department of IT policies of the [Ministry of Information Technology and Communications](#), dr.hab. Veaceslav Ursachi – coordinator of the Department of Engineering and Technological Sciences of the ASM, c.m. Constantin Gaidric – [Institute of Mathematics and Computer Sciences of ASM](#).

Professor, dr.hab. Anatol Gremalschi, program director at Institute of Public Policies made a presentation of the research study compiled by DISCUS experts, based on the findings of the scientific seminar held on May 26-27, 2015 focused on [ICT solutions for local services \(legal regulations\)](#).

Another presentation during the event was focused on the study visit in Poland (July 5-10, 2015). The aim of the visit was the exchange of experience, transfer of best practices from Poland to Moldova, networking and enhancing cooperation in the area of information society (focusing on local electronic services). Local public servants visited 4 towns in Poland, 10 institutions (local, regional and central level) where they attended over 20 presentations and were engaged in direct discussions with specialists. They made a presentation, sharing the gained experience and the results of the study visit.

Ion Cosuleanu, researcher at IDSI presented a set of recommendations on drawing up a plan of action for implementation of local electronic services. Based on the recommendations, the working teams (consisting of mayors, deputy mayors, secretaries of local councils and specialists) worked on developing action plans for implementation of local services, considered of high priority and common to several localities (e.g. issuance of certificates, cadastral extracts etc.).

The teams presented and evaluated their proposals based on the criteria explained by prof. Anatol Gremalschi:

- eligibility (the service you propose for digitization falls within your city hall competences?)
- relevance (do the citizens really need this service?)
- effectiveness (will it achieve its purpose of digitization?)
- efficiency (which will be the benefits? will they cover the cost of digitization?)
- durability.

2. General notions concerning public services

The term "service" (in the sense of providing services) refers to an activity (e.g. a service) by a provider, which is intended for the client (and therefore "serves" this customer).

Public service is a service which is provided by government to people living within its jurisdiction, either directly (through the public sector) or by financing provision of services. The term is associated with a social consensus (usually expressed through democratic elections) that certain services should be available to all, regardless of income.¹ Public services are seen as so important that for moral reasons their universal provision should be guaranteed. They may be associated with fundamental human rights (such as the right to water). A service is helping others with a specific need or want.²

In modern developed countries, the term "public services" (or "services of general interest") often includes: Electricity, Education, Emergency services, Environmental protection, Fire service, Gas, Health care, Law enforcement, Military, Postal service, Public broadcasting, Public library, Public security, Public transportation, Public housing, Social services, Telecommunications, Town planning, Waste management, Water supply network. These are services of public utility.

A public service may sometimes have the characteristics of a public good (being non-rivalrous and non-excludable), but most are services which may (according to prevailing social norms) be under-provided by the market. In most cases public services are services, i.e. they do not involve manufacturing of goods. They may be provided by local or national monopolies, especially in sectors which are natural monopolies.

They may involve outputs that are hard to attribute to specific individual effort and/or hard to measure in terms of key characteristics such as quality. They often require high levels of training and education. They may attract people with a public service ethos who wish to give something to the wider public or community through their work.

So, the public services can be provided by local or national authorities, depends on the service impact for citizens and the national regulation.

¹ McGregor, Eugene B., Jr, Campbell, A. K., Macy, John W., Jr, & Cleveland, H. (1982). Symposium: The public service as institution. *Public Administration Review*, 42(4), 304.

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Public_service

3. Legal framework of (local) public services in Moldova

There are several laws and some other governmental documents which sets the rules for delivery of public services.

In accordance with the Constitution of the Republic of Moldova, public administration in the administrative/territorial units is based on the principles of local autonomy, decentralization of public services, eligibility of local public administration authorities and on consultation of the citizens on local problems of special interest. The Law on Local Public Administration defines local public administration as a totality of local public authorities, created within the law, to meet general interests of the residents of a certain territorial administrative unit.

Law no. 436 from 28.12.2006 on local public administration, beside the general rules for organisation of local public authorities, its responsibilities, the Title X, art. 73 stipulates that:

Local public services are organised by local councils, at the proposal of the mayor in the decentralised spheres established for territorial-administrative units of Ist and IInd level, within the limits of available funds. The local council may decide contracting some local public services from individuals and private legal, under the law.

In the **Law no. 435 from 28.12.2006 on administrative decentralisation**, at art. 3 is mentioned through the principle of administrative decentralization, the principle of accountability of local public administration authorities, including, within their competence, the obligation to achieve minimum quality standards set by law in public service provision and public utility that are responsible. Also, the public authorities of different levels – Ist or IInd and central, can cooperate between them in order to ensure a better realisation of projects or providing public services.

The State Chancellery (art. 14) is responsible (together with other ministries and central authorities, as well as with associative structures of local public authorities) for setting minimum standards for cost and quality of public services and public utility and their monitoring.

The **Law no. 1402-XV from 24.10.2002 on public utility services** establishes unified legal framework for the establishment and organization of utility services in territorial-administrative units, including monitoring and control their operation. Public utility services ensure the supply / provision of the following services: water supply; thermal power; sewage and waste water and storm water; sanitation, greening settlements; providing local public transport; management of public and private housing.

The **Law no. 179-XVI from 10.07.2008 on public-private partnership** establishes the basic principles of public-private partnership forms and modalities, the procedure of initiation and realization of the public partner and the private partner rights and obligations. Public-private partnership is based on cooperation between private and public partners, aimed at increasing the efficiency of public property, each partner assuming the risks and concrete responsibilities. Under the law, the public-private partnership object can be any good, work, **public service** or function performed by the public partner, except as expressly permitted by law. Public-private

partnership can be formed having as object elements of infrastructure and / or existing **public services** or their creation.

Law no. 534 from 13.07.1995 on Concessions specifies that concessions object can be inclusive services of public interest - national or local.

The concession is a contract whereby the State or territorial administrative units assignment (send) to an investor (natural or legal person, including foreign) in return for a fee, the right to provide public services, taking over the management of the concessioned object, the presumptive risk and patrimonial responsibility.

Therefore, public services can be provided at national or local level. Public authorities, both central and local can provide public services by themselves or through public-private partnership contract, concessions.

According to **Public Services Reform Program**³ approved by the Government in 2014, re-engineering of public services is one of the most urgent priorities of the Government of Moldova, but also a major challenge that requires rethinking and transforming traditional patterns of activity of public authorities and institutions. The vertically organized public institutions that operate within the strict limits of the powers set by normative acts, are to be restructured into a single system that will remove institutional barriers, will develop horizontal linkages and cooperation instruments that provide efficient organization of public services for citizens and entrepreneurs and economical use of resources of central and local public authorities. This is necessary due to the rapid development of technological innovations, as well as the increasing demands of society. The Program identified two main groups of issues related to public service reform:

- The first group aimed at service system itself, covering such issues as quality of service, accessibility of information on services, the time required to obtain a specific service, the possibility to choose the channels for offering service to beneficiaries, respecting rule of law in the provision of services, reasonable costs for citizens and businesses, service culture, ensuring service delivery infrastructure, organization of economically efficient services.

- A second group of issues relates to public service reform itself and covers such issues as quality of reform policies by setting clear goals, principles and policy tools, activities and measures planned, correctness and their consistency with other government initiatives, primarily with e-transformation agenda, providing resources, establishing effective mechanisms for reform coordination and management, awareness by civil servants both at management level, and at the level of experts on essence and complexity of reform.

³ Public Services Reform Program for 2014-2016. Annex 1 at GD no. 122 from 18 .02.2014

4. E-services

e-services – public services provided to citizens by the authorities through electronic tools. These are paid or free of charge and can be ordered at distance, fast, simple and convenient.

Requirements for E-Services:

- ✓ Vision and clear objectives
- ✓ Organisational configuration
- ✓ Stakeholder participation
- ✓ Capacity building
- ✓ Project management
- ✓ Reducing the gap Reality - Design
- ✓ Public - private partnership
- ✓ Legal and Security Framework
- ✓ Monitoring and evaluation
- ✓ Citizen-oriented services

For e-services planning is recommended to follow a good balance of three main dimensions: public, electronic aspect and services, as is shown in Table no.1, bellow.

In other words, that 3 dimensions represent conceptualizing public e-services in 3D, as is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. **The Public e-Services Cube.**

Source: Ida Lindgren, PUBLIC E-SERVICES IN 3D, CONCEPTUALIZING PUBLIC E-SERVICES IN THREE DIMENSIONS, 9th Scandinavian Workshop on Electronic Government, Copenhagen February 9-10, 2012.

Table 1. Characteristics and Issues for Consideration in the Conceptualization of Public e-Services.

Source: Ida Lindgren and Gabriella Jansson, Electronic services in the public sector: A conceptual framework, 2013, Government Information Quarterly, (30), 2, 163-172.

Dimension	Main characteristics	Examples of issues for consideration in the conceptualization of public e-services
Public (Services and Organizations)	<p>The public ethos:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need to ensure comprehensive legal framework with different degrees of discretion. - Need to balance democratic and economic values, (accommodate principles of equality, responsiveness, availability and social inclusion, as well as cost efficiency). - Need to ensure legitimacy and accountability through democratic decision making, rule of law and efficient out-put. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Availability and fairness of public service provision, e.g. how is the public e-service being provided? - Voluntary vs. involuntary public services, e.g. who is the public e-service serving? - Economic vs. democratic values, e.g. what aims do the public e-service serve?
	<p>Lack of exit</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need to balance asymmetrical relationship with citizen, especially in monopolized or compulsory situations (legitimacy not based on choice) 	
	<p>Users as citizens, rather than consumers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need to ensure individual and political rights and obligations of citizenship. - Need to ensure services for all citizens (accommodate heterogeneity) 	
e-	<p>A technical artifact, constituted of</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Internet-based technology - Some degree of interaction -Connections to other information systems, e.g., back-office systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design and user related issues: e.g., - What are the users' experiences of interacting with the technology? - Why are public e-services adopted/not adopted by users? - Interoperability issues: e.g., to what other systems is the e-service connected? - Are these systems interoperable?
	<p>Should be evaluated in relation to its intended use and users, which implies that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A focus on users of technology is necessary - Accessibility and usability are important aspects 	
Services	<p>Service as a process</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Must be perceived as a process in which value is co-created by consumer and supplier 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Value creation: e.g., whose interests are served? For whom is value created? - Power symmetries: Asymmetrical relationships between user and supplier? - In what manner is the service performed? - What kind of information is used/exchanged? - Is the exchange reciprocal?
	<p>Service quality</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Must be assessed based on consumer's experience of the service 	

When the technology aspect of the public e-service is ignored there is a risk of getting caught in an overly optimistic view of technology as the given solution to all our problems, forgetting that technology offers both affordances and constraints to use. Not defining the technology also makes it difficult (1) to compare e-services used at present with services used in the past and future, (2) to evaluate the implementation and use of public e-services, and (3) understand the connections between e-service applications and interconnected information systems used to supply the e-service.

By highlighting e- in public e-services, it becomes clear that a public e-service is something different than just a public service mediated electronically. This is specifically the case for welfare services which are distributed on an individual basis. Public e-services usually do not involve the actual output, or end-product, of public policy, such as the teaching in schools or the medical treatment of a patient. Rather, it is the mediation of that service, the process through which this service is being communicated and accessed. Public e-services are in this sense a matter of information. In turn, by emphasizing the prefix public of public e-services, issues of availability and accessibility are placed in the foreground. When mediating public e-services, the constitutionally enshrined principle of equal treatment means promoting equal access. Public services have to be made available to different groups of citizens, with different needs.⁴

Public services must be evaluated on other grounds, such as **public value**. While private value can be estimated through financial measurements of profits, public value is related more to the achievement of objectives set by government programs and delivery of public services to citizens.

Public e-services can be provided in 2 main ways:

1. one way, public authority to citizen as external user:

Figure 2. **Public e-service with one-way communication from public agency to citizen**

Source: Göran Goldkuhl & Annie Röstlinger, Linköping University, Development of public e-services - a method outline, 7th Scandinavian Workshop on E-Government (SWEG-2010), January 27-28, 2010

2. two-way communication between public agency and citizen:

Figure 3. **Public e-service with two-way communication between public agency and citizen**

Source: Göran Goldkuhl & Annie Röstlinger, Linköping University, Development of public e-services - a method outline, 7th Scandinavian Workshop on E-Government (SWEG-2010), January 27-28, 2010

⁴ Ida Lindgren, Public e-services in 3D, conceptualizing public e-services in three dimensions, 9th Scandinavian Workshop on Electronic Government, Copenhagen February 9-10, 2012.

The public agency is of course responsible for setting up the e-service as a software application aimed for use by citizens. In this respect there is such a direction of the e-service (from provider to client). However concerning the information content of the e-service, there is a two-way direction of it: The agency communicates to the citizen and the citizen communicates to the agency. This makes e-services as special kinds of services: **Co-services**.

Figure 4. **Public e-service in context**

Source: Göran Goldkuhl & Annie Röstlinger, Linköping University, Development of public e-services - a method outline, 7th Scandinavian Workshop on E-Government (SWEG-2010), January 27-28, 2010

Public e-services realize communication between citizens and public agencies. Citizens get informed about rules and regulations, about rights and obligations and several other societal issues. Citizens can also communicate to agencies in different predefined ways; e.g. issuing applications for permits. The communication between citizens and public administrators are often not only mediated through e-services but also through internal IT-systems. Integrated e-service may also imply information exchange with IT-systems in other agencies or sometimes some other type of external organisation. Public e-service in context is depicted in figure 4.

When developing public e-services, we need to consider this context. There should be a focus on the e-service, but several other related issues need also to be taken into account.

One important issue is that e-services are parts of work processes. A process orientation should therefore be a feature of the e-service method. The e-service is also part of an IT-architecture. It is necessary to clarify issues of information exchange between the e-service and other related IT-systems. The public administration context of e-services implies different regulations and other types of norms. To know and relate to the regulations is important for achieving good processes and e-services. A normative investigation should be included in e-service development. E-service is communication (government-client communication). This e-communication is related to other kinds of communication; both human-to-human and other IT-mediated communication. Communication within a restricted domain will use linguistic

elements (concepts and terminology) particularly associated with this domain (workpractice). E-services are developed to support communication between several parties and it is important that both parties understand each other. A conceptual-linguistic inquiry should also be included in e-service development. This gives us five important aspects to consider during public e-service development:⁵

Table 2. **Method overview: Five aspects and two states**

	Diagnosis of preconditions (current state)	Co-design of processes & IT (future state)
Work processes	Analysis of current processes	Process re-design
Regulations & workpractice goals (norms)	Identification & analysis of norms: Analysis of regulations Analysis of goals	Norm prioritization Proposals of norm changes Norm validation of design proposals
Government-client communication	Analysis of forms & current web sites and e-services	E-service design (usability & functionality)
Workpractice language	Analysis of applied concepts (conceptual modelling)	Conceptual re-design
IS-architecture & message exchange	Analysis of current IS-architecture	Re-design of IS-architecture Design of message exchange

When developing e-services we must start the developing process by studying preconditions for the future e-service. This means that we should inquire the current situation. When the current state is clarified it is possible to begin the design of future solutions. We emphasise that this should be done as a co-design of business processes and IT-systems. Future e-services should be designed contextually and integrated with the surrounding activities. **To only replace a paper form with a digital one is not often an appropriate solution for an e-service.**

Instead of just making a simple digitalization of a paper form, an e-service development should imply a process redesign. The transfer to electronic communication should exploit potential of the IT medium. This should include making the work processes more efficient. The diagnosis of the current work processes should have revealed different problems. With inspiration from these problem and process descriptions, more efficient work processes could be designed.

It is important to have understandable and usable user interfaces for the citizens as external users. The regulative character of public administration needs to be taken into account. The new e-service should be well integrated into the existing IT infrastructure. The potential of IT as an enabler of process redesign should also be considered.

Public services based on ICT - Benefits for applicants:

- Easier access to information and services
- Quality and cheaper services
- Easier access to other institutions and assistance for this reason
- Simplified and standard forms

⁵ Göran Goldkuhl & Annie Röstlinger, Linköping University, Development of public e-services - a method outline, Paper accepted to the 7th Scandinavian Workshop on E-Government (SWEG-2010), January 27-28, 2010

- Save time
- Save money (eg. for transport)

Criteria for pre-selection of ICT-based services:

- ✓ cost of implementation (within available resources)
- ✓ period of implementation (up to 12-18 months);
- ✓ e-services for citizens (G2C) and business (G2B) and less services for LPA;
- ✓ minimum back office infrastructure available;
- ✓ business processes of e-service must be defined and functional.
- ✓ urgency and relevance;
- ✓ number of beneficiaries;
- ✓ back office readiness level;
- ✓ level of complexity;
- ✓ legal and regulatory framework;
- ✓ leadership and political will;
- ✓ readiness of the beneficiary;
- ✓ sustainability;
- ✓ external factors (EU integration agenda etc.).

5. E-Services in Moldova - the actual situation

Republic of Moldova has made significant progress in the digitization of public services at the central level. The success of these activities creates promising prerequisites for the digitisation of the local public services, by providing access to registries and databases of central authorities, by transfer of experience, by adapting existing technical solutions to the specific local context. However, at the moment, a consolidated vision on local public services that could be digitized, as well as future institutional framework, to ensure their digitization, don't exist.

The e-Governance Center is the institution responsible on behalf of the Government for the implementation of the e-Transformation Agenda (supported by the World Bank, was adopted in 2011) and set up an unique platform for public services provided by the central authorities - <http://www.servicii.gov.md> portal. This platform functions as an electronic catalogue for public services provided by the authorities dedicated to citizens and the business. The main purpose of this platform is to offer brief, correct, accessible and complete information on the public services available in the Republic of Moldova.

On the platform, you can find information regarding both electronic services, as well as traditional services. The visitors can find the description of the services, the set of documents required for this services, the schedule of the services, the costs and the implementation duration. They can also find contact details for more information and the forms that have to be completed by the citizens in electronic format, including completion's guidance.

The platform is divided into service categories for:

- Citizens (information and petition, finance and taxes, licences and special permits etc.)
- Businesses (taxes, reports, confirming acts, permissive acts, etc.)
- Visitors (Moldovan citizenship, entry and stay in the Republic of Moldova)
- Life scenarios (emigration, immigration, business initiation, real estate, creating a family, health, studies).

Currently, there are 481 services on the portal, of which 105 are e-Services (on-line services) with data opened for access. The Republic of Moldova Government is determined to transform all traditional counter services into e-services by 2020, through the „Open Government action plan” and the „Government technological modernisation strategy”. In this way, the citizens will be able to access over 500 e-services.

However, at the moment most of 105 e-Services on the platform are rather informative then fully electronic service providing.

The top 10 most accessed e-services on the platform: (at 10.11.2015)

1. Issue criminal records of individuals
2. Free access to data from real estate register
3. Licensing of road transport
4. Check IDNO
5. Check IDNP
6. Release of information from the National Archives and the Archives of Social and Political Organizations of the Republic of Moldova
7. The identity card of the citizen of RM / electronic citizen ID card RM
8. Licensing of activity for building and / or engineering facilities, installations and public utility networks, reconstructions, restorations
9. Check the number of people with the same name / surname
10. Licensing medical assistance by private medical institutions

Generalization of the existing problems from the beneficiaries’ perspective includes⁶:

1) Incomplete information posted on the public institutions websites. In most cases to benefit from the necessary service, recipients are forced to visit in person the servicing institutions.

According to survey results, in 2013 - more than 50% beneficiaries have recognized that the information on the website about the required service was insufficient.

2) Narrow institutional approach and isolation of public institutions in organizing services. The beneficiary continues to act as a courier, ensuring the exchange of documents between public institutions. Although the interoperability of public registers is being implemented, it works only in isolated cases, requiring significant time and additional economic costs to citizens and businesses.

⁶ Public Services Reform Program for 2014-2016. Annex 1 at GD no. 122 from 18 .02.2014

According to 2013 survey results - to get a distinct service, more than 30% of beneficiaries had to visit more than 3 institutions.

3) Lack of systematic procedures and practices to assess the administrative burden. The regulatory framework, which sets out the procedure for obtaining service provides requirements that might yield without additional risks, but systematic assessment and identification of excessive existing procedures and processes are carried out only in separate cases, particularly in international technical assistance projects.

4) Arbitrary inclusion of additional requirements beyond of normative acts provisions (laws, government decisions, decisions by local authorities) established by the institutions' internal instructions on the service. This requires the need for repeated visits to institutions to submit documents not covered by legal acts and not included in the lists of documents posted on institutions' websites. This way the time needed to get a service is increasing.

5) Lack of uniform and transparent principles for establishing tariffs for paid services. Prices for services are perceived by most people as arbitrary or unreasonable. According to the survey results in 2013 - more than 58% of beneficiaries considered the tariffs for services as unjustified.

6) The existence of unofficial supplementary payments claimed by beneficiaries. The 2011 Survey, conducted by the International Republican Institute (IRI), Baltic Surveys / The Gallup Organization, showed that additional informal payments constituted the usual way of solving the problems of citizens interacting with public institutions in more than 80% of cases. According to the 2013 Survey, 47% of respondents admitted that unofficial payments were requested in the delivery of a service.

The most common services delivered at the local level are:

- certificate of family composition,
- certificate regarding the payment of taxes,
- certificate of residence,
- certificates of possession (lack) of agricultural land,

Out of the 22 services delivered at the local level, respondents mentioned as necessary the following **online services/documents**:

- certificate regarding the payment of taxes,
- certificate of residence,
- certificate of family composition,
- excerpt from the Cadastre registry,
- excerpts from the household account.

According to respondents' opinion, some services such as: marriage registration act and possession of property act, should be delivered traditionally, due to required presence of several applicants.⁷

⁷ Research Study "Administrative public services at local level: diagnostic and transformation opportunities"

Table 3. Problems identified VS potential e-services formulated by relevant studies/ public servants

Problems identified VS potential e-services formulated by:

Participants at the 1st DISCUS workshop from March 17-18, Chisinau	Joint Integrated Local Development Program (of UNDP):
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Certificates issuing (family composition etc.) - Archive services / lack of record keeping of services - Cadastral Excerpts (building permits, excerpts from property register etc.) - Certificates on Tax debts - Social Insurance - Services are provided in different offices/no one stop-shop office - Lack of networking (IS) between raions (LPAII) and villages (LPAI) - Decisional transparency/ lack of information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Certificates issuing (family composition etc.) - Lack of digitalized registers - Archive services / lack of record keeping of service - Cadastral Excerpts (building permits, excerpts from property register etc.) - Lack of interoperability - Certificates on Tax debts - Lack of access to relevant information source - Social insurance - Services are provided in different offices/no one stop-shop office - Lack of information systems for LPA and interoperability between decentralised services - Lack of on-line/off-line communication between different public servants from different institutions - Lack of networking (IS) between raions (LPAII) and villages (LPAI)
USAID LGSP project:	Participants at the Workshop from September 22 - 23, Chisinau:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Services are provided in different locations - Insufficient information - Multiple visits for services application and delivery - Insufficient accounting of services (lack of registers) - Old equipment and inefficient service delivery (costly) - The risk of discontinuity - services delivered by one person - Low level security when storing documents - Inefficient document circulation (lack of automation) - Limited communication and data exchange between LPAs and other institutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Issuing certificates from the Population Registry (s. Persecina) - On-line Applications - On-line Payment (tax for kindergarten) - Web page development - citizens do not have access to information and services (group no. 4 - for Saiti village)

6. Recommendations - useful/ practical tips

From project idea to e-service:

Figure 5. From project idea to e-service

Source: Ion Cosuleanu, GUIDELINES FOR THE PRACTICAL ASSIGNMENT, DISCUS Workshop: Electronic Local Public Services, September 22-23, 2015, Chisinau - http://discus.idsi.md/sites/default/files/Guide_practical_assignment_workshop_22-23.09.2015.pdf

Table 4. **Project Proposal Matrix**

Project Description	Indicators	Source of Verification	Assumptions
<p>Overall objective: The broad development impact to which the project contributes – at a national or sectoral level (provides the link to the policy and/or sector programme context)</p>	<p>Measures the extent to which a contribution to the overall objective has been made. Used during evaluation. However, it is often not appropriate for the project itself to try and collect this information.</p>	<p>Sources of information and methods used to collect and report it (including who and when/how frequently).</p>	
<p>Purpose: The development outcome at the end of the project – more specifically the expected benefits to the target group(s)</p>	<p>Helps answer the question ‘How will we know if the purpose has been achieved’? Should include appropriate details of quantity, quality and time.</p>	<p>Sources of information and methods used to collect and report it (including who and when/how frequently)</p>	<p>Assumptions (factors outside project management’s control) that may impact on the purpose-objective linkage</p>
<p>Results: The direct/tangible results (good and services) that the project delivers, and which are largely under project management’s control</p>	<p>Helps answer the question ‘How will we know if the results have been delivered’? Should include appropriate details of quantity, quality and time.</p>	<p>Sources of information and methods used to collect and report it (including who and when/how frequently)</p>	<p>Assumptions (factors outside project management’s control) that may impact on the result-purpose linkage</p>
<p>Activities: The tasks (work programme) that need to be carried out to deliver the planned results <i>(optional within the matrix itself)</i></p>	<p><i>(sometimes a summary of resources/means is provided in this box)</i></p>	<p><i>(sometimes a summary of costs/budget is provided in this box)</i></p>	<p>Assumptions (factors outside project management’s control) that may impact on the activity-result linkage</p>

Table 5:

Model Action plan for implementation (service name)

Problem: (problem description)				
General objective: (from Documents on strategic development of the locality, rayon, region, country)				
Goal: Implementing service (name) in LPA (locality)				
Activity/Sub-activity	Period	Responsible	Progress indicators	Monitoring Evaluation
	Start: End:		Product: Result:	
	Start: End:		Product: Result:	Intermediate: Ex-post:

6.1 Comments and Recommendations of the Polish expert

Working plan of a town/village hall in terms of e-services implementation

The plan is based on:

- TOGAF
- Prince2
- ITIL
- ISO27001 principles.

Each step should not be very complicated – usually 1 page concept will suffice provided there is no problem in the topic.

Table 6. Steps for e-services planning

<i>Step 1. Create an e-service vision</i>	<i>Step 2. Refine the project</i>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Analyze existing strategy (if any of LPA), and identify goals of a LPA. 2. Define high level vision of e-services. 3. Identify problems that are to be solved 4. Identify main stakeholders in terms of e-Services (parties that can be interested – positively and negatively in the project), their concerns and objectives. 5. Asses demand for the proposed eService. 6. Assess the risks of the proposed eService. 7. Define propositions to stakeholders to address their concerns and objectives. 8. Define “elevator speech” to gain support (very short description of the idea possible to pass during elevator travel). 9. Work out consensus of desired outcome. 10. Gain approval of the eService idea. 	<p><i>Identify Baseline Architecture:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Existing procedures and write them in BPMN notation (or other) 2. Existing applications, databases (even in paper) and hardware 3. Existing personnel 4. Existing forms 5. Legal constraints (i.e. if some law prohibits an action to be undertaken) 6. Budgetary constraints (i.e. In terms of proposed investment) <p><i>Develop Target Architecture:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. Choose appropriate eService level 8. Define administrative procedures using e-service 9. Define new applications, forms and databases concept 10. Define target skills 11. Write down new instructions if needed 12. Asses the costs. 13. Perform gap analysis – identify action to move from baseline to target in terms of procedures, IT, training, legal framework and budget. 14. Propose the timetable for the project. 15. Make final budgetary assessment. 16. Develop communication plan with stakeholders. 17. Write down all the settlements in Document

	<p>Initiating Project Document</p> <p>18. Gain final approval</p>
<p><i>Step 3. Implement e-Service</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop electronic forms. 2. Develop back office software. 3. Integrate e-Service with existing databases/software. 4. Train the staff at LPA <p><i>Test the e-Service:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Internal test (within LPA) 6. External test (with selected members of public). 7. Provide security tests against ISO27001 appendix – formulate Statement of Application (SoA). 8. Do OWASP10 penetration testing against most common vulnerabilities. 9. Go live with the public. 10. Promote the e-Service and communicate with stakeholders. 11. Document the e-Service. 	<p><i>Step 4. Maintain e-Service</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Settle appropriate Service Level Agreement (please keep in mind that not all the e-Service have to be maintained 24/7) 2. Develop procedures in case e-Service is down. 3. Provide the helpdesk for the e-Service. 4. Monitor eService utilization. 5. Test periodically against known vulnerabilities (OWASP 10). 6. Monitor legal and social environment to assure the e-Service is still needed. 7. Evaluate technical problems that arise. 8. Monitor e-Service effectiveness. 9. Keep people informed about the e-Service <p>Gather ideas of improvement -> Step 1</p>

Short analysis of the participant's presentations/ideas presented during the workshop from September

First of all it has to be stressed that the main goal of work in groups during September workshop was to envisage the participants the problems that arise during the implementation of e-service. This goal was accomplished as participants pointed out most important aspects that have to be taken care of.

It has to be stressed however that most of the problems regarding implementation of IT systems are common. That is why it is important to use common methodologies and standards. This enables to focus the attention to the specific problems. Those issues usually are no more than 5% of the project – however they may jeopardize the whole initiative.

In brief: it is no use to push on the door, that is already open.

Returning to the work groups, one very important conclusion arises: the cornerstone of any e-service is proper website. Analysis made during workshop pointed out that few LPA in Moldova do not have any kind of website. In other cases there are some problems of existing web pages: often they are not properly maintained, sometimes out of date or use awkward layout.

Therefore it seems that two most important tasks to be performed are:

- Implementation of website in LPA which lack such a device,
- Standardization of existing portals.

The latter issue brings out the idea of common layout available to every LPA. The good example is the CMS presented during workshops.

Utilization of common CMS requires assurance that the following issued are addressed:

- CMS itself should be tested against known security issues (OWASP10),
- CMS should be validated against WCAG 2.0 recommendations (AA level preferably),
- CMS should be analysed from the point of view of User Experience (UX) recommendations,
- CMS should enable utilization of various graphic formats suitable for each LPA.

It is also worthwhile to mention that implementation of website requires implementation of procedures of keeping it up to date and properly maintained against agreed SLA contract.

The recommendations that arise are the following:

1. It is important to convince appropriate ministries to issue instructions on expected IT standards in LPA in Moldova.
2. LPA staff should be able to have a comprehensive training in leading IT standards like Prince, ITIL, TOGAF, ISO etc.
3. The first step for e-Services in Moldova should be the implementation of standardized and secure CMS utilizing WCAG 2.0 and UX recommendations.

6.2 Comments and Recommendations of the Czech expert

Generalization of building ISPA oriented to LPA e-services

To achieve success i.e. e-services are developed and provided with minimal cost and characterized by high efficiency (satisfaction of citizens), it is necessary to create conditions for building design and follow solution of e-services. It means focusing on the following areas:

1. Creating national environment for ISPA.
2. Create an information system for data elements in public administration
3. Create standards for ISPA in the spirit of the applicable technical standards and legislation.
4. Create a mechanism to verify compliance with these rules.
5. Certification of compliance with the obligations of the contractor IS.

Of course working out documents (technical standards, regulations, implementing regulations, laws etc.) to the above activities is not, and can not be a one-off event. It's a lengthy process requiring the cooperation of many parties.

Working out of government services and their computerization

1. Definition and **creation of tasks** undertaken by public administration.
2. Development of **methodology** for the possibility of application solutions and bindings between tasks.
3. Implementation of **bindings** between tasks within the internal integration.
4. Implementation of the bindings between **internal and external** systems.

Only then on this basis, it is possible to deal with the possibilities solutions providing **electronic services** to citizens.

This process of building will illustratively discussed below.

Ad.1. In order to define and create the task we need to have (or create) agenda. For example, the provision of data from the registry of real property or payment for municipal services. The input data are usually provided in the forms of either paper or electronic. Data on the agenda are somehow processed either system "question-answer" or computation. Outputs are typically provided in paper or electronic form (usually form). This process is illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6.

Ad.2. The fundamental finding, that we should take into account is the fact that the provision of services is a cost to everything. Thus, first of all, we should resolve the relationship provided service to accounting and how this relationship will be realized. In our case, the citizen will pay (or not pay if the service is provided free of charge) in cash to the cashier as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7.

Ad.3. Hereby we have exhausted the possibilities of the agenda in the provision of services in that area and at that level. To be expanded our ability to providing services for the citizens from multiple locations, we engage in our activity bank, i.e. external components, see in Figure 8.

Figure 8.

Ad. 4. Now we have created internal and external bindings, and so the conditions for us to be able to deal with computerization, in other words providing services electronically. At this point, we can deal how we will implement these bindings, and through these bindings to provide services. Whether using web interface or SMS, or by e-mail or in the city center of electronic services etc., see Figure 9.

Figure 9.

From the above it follows that putting into the operation (into the life) of our intention to provide electronic services (either national or local layer) we must develop and implement standards for information systems of public administration. These are:

- a) Technical standards relating to the hardware, network infrastructure and software:
 - 1. Standards for interconnection.
 - 2. Standards for access to e-services.
 - 3. Web services standards.
 - 4. Standards for data integration.
- b) Standards of accessibility and functionality of web pages relating to the application software according to the law.
- c) Standards for using files relating to the data exchange formats.
- d) Standards terminology of electronic services related to network infrastructure.
- e) Security standards applicable to hardware, network infrastructure, middleware and data:
 - 1. Standards for architecture management.
 - 2. The minimum technical standards of security.
- f) Data standards relating to the data, data elements, value sets of data elements, classifiers and registers.
- g) Standards of electronic services of public administration relating to the data, data elements, value sets of data elements, classifiers, registers and application software according to the law.
- h) Project management standards relating to the procedures and conditions related to the creation, development and operation of information systems in public administration.

These standards should be developed and should be publicly accessible.

Based on these standards (are issued by organizations including ISO, IEC, CEN, ETSI) it must be processed for each e-service appropriate methodological solutions.

6.3 Comments and Recommendations from Slovak expert

The information age is bringing new requirements to the work of people, including public administration. This work is changing from traditional way of paper forms to electronical forms, including more proactive, with more frequent communication with clients. Speaking about clients I mean citizens, entrepreneurs, NGOs as well as public administration itself. All these groups can interact with each other and have various roles and positions.

The information age is bringing new technical solutions, but these must be used in the right way and hand in hand with changes of clients' approaches, by applying good rules in processes of proposing and implementing projects leading to new services. New services should avoid duplications and repeated requests of documents from clients. Public administration maintains many of them and is publishing them for clients. So there is no reason to ask the documents (data) again in case of various requests or obligations of clients to the public administration. New services should bring the possibility of 24/24 access of clients to eServices of public administration and should bring clients additional benefits, such as proactive communication/services of public administration.

Above written targets are not easy to achieve, both in the state and local administration. The reason is, that everything is linked with everything and good quality, reliability and timeliness of data is crucial. This aspect is increasing taking into account the fact that various offices of public administration are responsible for various types of data according to their competences. The quality of the whole chain depends on the weakest part. It means, if one type of data needed for the whole process is weak or of bad quality/reliability, the overall result is of problematic quality. Good communication between these offices to avoid duplications and multivalency of data is crucial and must be regulated by **enactments, rules and standards**.

Because the main clients databases in each country are maintained by the central government and their institutions, **it is not easy to start to develop eServices on local level**. If we don't want to spend sources and achieve weak or bad quality results, it is important to rethink all aspects based on processes and needed data, taking into account their accessibility and quality. So when deciding to start the planning and development of new eServices in local level authorities, it is important to use complex approach and

- to rethink own situation (from side of data, competencies, personnel, etc.),
- to research the accessibility of data from national level and
- to describe

own Vision for building e-Services, e.g.: We want to build and reach

- increasing the number of **Efficient** and **Effective e-Services** for:
 - our **Office**
 - our **Inhabitants / Institutions**

to decrease the amount of work or obligations and for

- increasing **Transparency** and
- increasing public **Participation**
- etc.

Based on the Vision of own Office to develop the **Concept** based on:

- own **Competences** and related **Processes**, taking into account:
 - situation with **guaranteed DATA**
 - ❖ own data or

- ❖ data of other institutions
 - and online / offline **access to DATA**
- and
 - existing plan of **central e-Services** building (types, schedule, how will they interact with plan of my e-Services plan, etc.)

By preparing such Concept, one should think on:

1. Architecture of the whole system
2. Communication and Security
 - safe and clear **Identification** of client
 - secure **Communication channels**
 - web
 - interface adapted for mobile devices
 - way of reliable **Administration** of system
 - data storage / cloud
 - sharing of data between systems and processes
 - technical aspects, e.g. infrastructure, accessibility, ...
 - harmonisation with **Administrative system** and **Procedures**
3. Responsibility
 - personal
 - institutional
4. History
 - **WHAT** was done, by **WHOM**, **WHEN** and **WHY**
5. Sustainability (life cycle, updates, annual costs, ...)

Than SET

- list of eServices and
- Schedule

FIND

- Sources and
- Coalitions

Coalitions means to agree with other local authorities about the same approach and same plan and agree about implementation, by which could be shared the developed tools in all authorities creating such coalition.

Before finally deciding on the order of services development, it is necessary to rethink the balance between:

- **BENEFITS** from e-Services (savings, higher quality / availability / ...)
- and
- **COSTS**

it means the **value of the whole plan** and based on

- to prioritise **e-Services** and
- to develop an **Action Plan**

Realisation of this Action Plan should be assessed by a **Feasibility Study** and based on its results **Implementation** can be initiated.

During this process it is important to take care of the following aspects:

- owner of the process and clients' approach (to have owner and to give him/her adequate competences)
- safety
- data, architecture, broadband, development, testing
- legislation
- agreements, procurements
- neighbourhood – interoperability – SOA
- timetable, management, maintenance
- sources
- awareness, trainings
- user friendly approach, helpdesk, clients' centers
- sustainability – loop: assessment, updates, change management

This way we can

- save SOURCES
- share RESOURCES for many e-Services
- offer services which are required or can bring the fastest effect
- support POLICY of our Office
- bring satisfied VOTERS
- etc.

6.4 Comments and Recommendations from the national expert

There is a certain progress in the implementation of ICT-based services at the local level, however their development lately encountered major financial issues related to the unstable political and economic situation in the country as a whole.

Another issue is related to frequent change of staff and therefore a lack of institutional memory, which results in a lack of continuity in promoting technologies.

As example in this regard is the Automated Information System of territorial administration, which although aired as a pilot project in many LPAs, was not implemented. As the issue remained unresolved, an analysis of the situation should be carried out in order to propose an approach, based on the new instruments now available through the e-Government Center.

The seminars and workshops organized in the framework of the DISCUS platform prove the need for further capacity building activities for local government officials, through practical exercises geared to the needs of local authorities. These exercises, stemming from the analysis of problems and identification of necessary solutions and activities, are of utmost importance.

Providing information on consulting opportunities when necessary, regarding the opportunities offered by the e-Government Center Platform, the use of best practices from other LPAs, examples provided by experts from the Visegrad countries, all these contribute substantially to improving the performance of local officials.

However, regardless of the efforts, ICTs are poorly implemented at the local level, due to a lack of funds and human resources, as well as an IT consulting institution for local authorities. DISCUS platform proved that a permanent platform for the exchange of information,

documents, forms, etc., to support and guide the LPAs in developing ICT-based services, is necessary and beneficial.

Unfortunately, local government representatives know very little about assistance projects financed by development partners and do not have capacities for developing project proposals.

The implementation of new technologies at the local level requires setting up as medium to long-term priority the development of ICTs in local development strategies and other policy documents of municipalities/local councils, district, as well as allocation of resources in this regard.

Final conclusions

1. In the Republic of Moldova the process of local public services digitization is at the initial stage, the few existing attempts refer mostly to the use of ICT for disseminating information, pertaining to the activity of local public administration and informing citizens.

2. One of the priorities in the digitization of local public services should be their prioritization depending on the level of demand and identification of those public services, which when digitised would have significant social and economic effects.

3. It is necessary to perform a detailed inventory and a clear delineation of public services provided by local authorities and those provided by the central government, when the local authority only plays the role of agent/operator providing the service.

4. A unique public policy is needed for digitizing local public services. This policy should address all aspects of this process: normative-legal, institutional, technical, organizational.

5. The digitization of local public services should be started with the digitization of all processes within local authorities themselves.

6. Digitisation of local public services requires standard technological solutions. The development of such technological solutions is the responsibility of the central government.

Final Recommendations

1. The ICT tools are still unsatisfactorily implemented at the local level, due to lack of funding and human resources. The government support is necessary in implementation of information systems at the level of local administrative authorities and in the institutionalization of the center of IT consulting for local authorities.

2. The DISCUS platform maintained by IDSI supported by the e-Government Center and relevant Central public authorities could serve as reference platform for sharing information, documents, forms, etc., supporting and guiding LPA in building ICT based services.

3. More effective and efficient coordination and synchronisation of donors assistance projects for local authorities is necessary to exclude overlapping and duplication of efforts and activities.

4. Continuing support for LPA in ICT and project management capacity building, use of tested applications, document management systems, etc.

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Annex 1. Workshop Agenda

Agenda

Workshop: Local Public e-Services

22 - 23.09.2015 - Chisinau, Moldova

Labour Institute, Room no. 6, 10 Zimbrului str., Chisinau, Moldova, 2024

1st Day – September 22			
Time	nr	Topic/presentation	Speaker/expert/moderator
9.30 -10.00	Arrival & Registration		
		Workshop opening	Igor Cojocaru, IDSI (M)
10.00 - 10.10	1.1	Opening remarks & overview of the Agenda	Igor Cojocaru Director, Information Society Development Institute
10.15- 10.25	1.2	Welcome speech	Acad. Ion Tighineanu , Vice-president Academy of Sciences of Moldova
10.25 - 10.35	1.3	Welcome speech	Andrei Cușcă , Ministry of Information Technology and Communications
10.40 - 10.50	1.4	Welcome speech	Ceauș Sergiu , Deputy General Secretary of the Government
10.50 - 11.25	1.5	Presentation of the II nd project study research based on the seminar (from may) findings	Anatol Gremalschi , Program director Institute for Public Policy (IPP)
		Q&A session	
11.30 - 12.00		Pauză de cafea	
		Study visit to Poland - lessons learnt	
12.00 - 12.35	2.1	Study visit to Poland - July 5 - 10, 2015	Anastasia Stefanita , ISDI & participants
	2.2	Discussions with participants at the study visit	
		Action Plan: Local Public e-Services	
12.40 - 13.00	3.1	Recommendations for writing an action plan (template, suggestions)	Ion Coșuleanu , ISDI V4 experts
13.00 - 13.40	3.2	Explaining the exercise/task.	Anatol Gremalschi , Program

		Formation of the working teams. Formation the Evaluation Commission.	director Institute for Public Policy (IPP) Ion Coşuleanu, ISDI
13.40 - 14.30		Lunch	
	4	Working in groups	
14.40 - 16.40	4.1	Working in groups (coordinated by DISCUS experts)	
16.20 - 16.50		Coffee break & Discussions	
16.50 - 18.00	4.2	Working groups presentations	Ion Coşuleanu, ISDI
18.00 - 19.00		Networking event	
2nd Day – September 23			
		Final action plans	
09.00 - 09.20	5.1	Analyse of the working groups presentations. Discussions.	DISCUS experts
09.25 - 09.45	5.2	Evaluation Commission opinion. Selection of the best two action plans.	Ion Coşuleanu, ISDI
09.50 - 10.40	5.3	Work in 2 groups on finishing the 2 selected action plans	DISCUS experts
10.45 - 11.00	5.4	Recommendations on finalizing plans	Anatol Gremalschi, IPP
11.00 - 11.30		Coffee break	
		Project: eServices & document circulation	
11.30 - 11.45	6.1	Presentation of the project: eServices of Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of Slovakia	Vlado Benko , expert from Slovakia
11.45 - 12.15	6.2	System of electronic document circulation in public management ANOFM & Czech partners	Stanislav Horák , expert in document circulation, DATAB consult, s.r.o., Czech Republic
12.15 - 12.30		Experts answers to participants' questions	DISCUS experts
12.30 - 12.45		Final discussions & conclusions of the event	
12.50 - 13.15		Handing participation certificates	
13.15 - 13.30		Feedback questionnaire	
		Final organisational issues	
13.30 - 14.30		Lunch	
14.30 - 15.00		Wrap-up & Departure	

DISCUS is a project coordinated by the [Information Society Development Institute](#), with the support of partners from Visegrad countries and funded under the [International Visegrad Fund](#)

Annex 2. Project Factsheet no.5

DISCUS

Workshop: Electronic Local Public Services

september 22-23
2015
Chisinau

• Visegrad Fund

> 50
participants

36
town halls

10
presentations

4
working groups

**Research study
Ro & Eng**

